

One 4Health SURVEILLANCE

Deliverable D3.1 Evaluation Plan

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Document history

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About this document

This document is Deliverable D3.1, Evaluation Plan, of OH4Surveillance. This document includes a description of the evaluation activities during the implementation of the project as well as the main indicators, target values and methods of verification. The evaluation activities will focus on action level, project level and surveillance activity level indicators.

Background

The majority of new emerging infectious diseases that affect humans are zoonoses, infections that can be transmitted between animals and humans. There are many factors that drive the emergence and spread of zoonotic diseases, and it has become evident that animal health, human health and the environment are interconnected. Therefore, there is a pressing need for more rapid and effective responses to zoonotic diseases, which can be achieved with a conceptual shift from siloed approaches towards a One Health approach. The surveillance on the animal health side and in the environment need to be scaled up to set up a One Health surveillance for emerging and re-emerging pathogens. Ideally, this is done in collaboration across countries.

The general objective of OH4Surveillance ('Setting up a coordinated surveillance under the One Health approach') is to support the participating countries to set up and scale up One Health surveillance to priority pathogens in an efficient, coordinated and collaborative manner. The project includes capacity building and surveillance activities.

OH4Surveillance comprises of 11 beneficiaries and 11 affiliated entities and is coordinated by Statens Serum Institut (SSI).

Work package 3 of OH4Surveillance is responsible for the evaluation of the project and works closely with other work packages. The key strategy applied is that evaluation takes place throughout the project, thus allowing addressing relevant observations during the project lifetime. In line with this, evaluation was among the key topics discussed at Kick-off meeting of OH4Surveillance, held in Copenhagen, Denmark, on February 27-28, 2024.

The evaluation activities of OH4Surveillance will focus on action level, project level and surveillance activity level indicators. The methods of verification are adapted to each indicator. The Key Performance Indicators reflect the action level indicators and have numerical target values. The results of the evaluation activities will be reported in the Interim Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.2) and at the Final Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.3).

Evaluation indicators

Action level indicators

The specific action level indicators for reporting purposes were specified in the *Invitation to submit proposals*:

- The number of zoonotic pathogens/group of pathogens covered by the surveillance activity;*
- Number of pilot Member States involved;*
- Number of capacity building initiatives;*
- Number of meetings at national level to promote One Health approach in the awareness components, coordination and national data collection and assessment;*
- Number of diagnostic samples collected, tested with results reported to EFSA;*
- Number of yearly summaries delivered to EFSA of the national assessment across animal and public health and the environment in a One Health approach;*
- Member States participation to the EFSA/ECDC overall EU assessment of risks identified as well as to the yearly re-prioritisation exercise by EFSA.*

Data on the action level indicators are explicitly included in regular reporting to HaDEA, as well as in the Interim Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.2) and at the Final Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.3).

Project level indicators

Project levels indicators are the Specific Objectives that OH4Surveillance aims to reach to address the key needs identified, and the related Key Performance Indicators. The evaluation strategy is to continuously work towards reaching the Specific Objectives and to monitor the progress.

Need 1: Setting up and scaling up One Health surveillance

There is a need to set up and scale up surveillance for emerging and re-emerging pathogens on the animal health side and in the environment to inform the public health sector. This need can be optimally addressed in collaboration across countries, as the threats are cross-border health threats.

There is also a need to identify the problems posed by emerging zoonotic diseases in terms of public health risks to respond to and to prepare for them, and for this, a consortium encompassing several countries is optimal.

Specific Objective 1: Obtain an overview of current One Health surveillance and surveillance needs for selected priority pathogens in the participating countries

Specific Objective 2: Set up and scale up One Health surveillance activities addressing regional and country-specific needs

Specific Objective 3: Contribute to harmonising and collaborative approaches across countries to prepare for cross-border health threats

Need 2: Collaboration and sharing to avoid duplication of efforts and to ensure synergies

Setting up a coordinated One Health surveillance is a co-creation process, and there are several initiatives at national, regional and international levels that address this. Coordinating the setting up and scaling up of One Health surveillance is optimally done as a consortium to minimise the risk of duplication of efforts, to ensure synergies, and to facilitate learning from each other. Collaboration across partners, across countries, with other projects and initiatives, as well as with stakeholders are crucial to ensure complementarity, alignment, and division of roles and responsibilities. Collaboration is the key, and coordinated collaboration is the optimal approach.

Specific Objective 4: Establish structures and processes for collaboration and sharing of experiences among countries participating in OH4Surveillance

Specific Objective 5: Establish structures and processes for collaboration with stakeholders at national, EU and international levels

Specific Objective 6: Establish structures and processes for disseminating experiences to support countries that are not part of OH4Surveillance

Each Specific Objective is related to Key Performance Indicator(s), as presented in Table 1. Progress on the project level indicators is included in regular reporting to HaDEA, as well as in the Interim Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.2) and at the Final Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.3).

Table 1. Key Performance Indicators of OH4Surveillance.

Key Performance Indicators	Baseline	Target	Related Specific Objectives
KPI 1 – Number of zoonotic pathogens covered by the surveillance activities	ND	At least one in each country	1, 2
KPI 2 – Number of countries involved	0	11	2
KPI 3 – Number of capacity building initiatives	0	5	2
KPI 4 – Number of meetings to promote One Health	0	National level: at least one in each country International level: 1	4,5,6
KPI 5 – Number of diagnostic samples collected, tested, and results reported to EFSA	0	>100	2
KPI 6 – Number of yearly summaries delivered to EFSA	0	3 from each country	2
KPI 7 – Number of scientific publications	0	At least 3 scientific publications.	6
KPI 8 – Number of exchanging experiences of work that is conducted during the project duration, between countries	Not applicable	5	4
KPI 9 – Number of tags in social media	None	OH4Surveillance account tagged at least 100 times on social media.	6

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Surveillance activity level indicators

The third evaluation level is the surveillance activity level, focusing on specific surveillance activities targeting a specific pathogen or disease. The evaluation strategy is to apply an established tool for evaluating One Healthness of surveillance systems, and to repeat the evaluation to monitor improvements.

The tool applied is OH-EpiCap tool (Tegegne et al., 2023), which was developed during the One Health European Joint Programme (European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, Grant Agreement No. 773830) Joint Integrative Project MATRIX. The tool can be applied to any system where some multi-sectoral collaboration exists at any step of the surveillance, regardless of the level of formalisation of the surveillance activity. The evaluation consists of three dimensions, each targeting four indicators.

Utilising OH-EpiCap tool as part of a large project is innovative, as the project defines a common framework, timeline and specific aims, which enable comparable evaluations across pathogens and countries. In OH4Surveillance, the timing is interesting as the participating countries are setting up and scaling up the surveillance activities in parallel, and the overall aim is pre-defined: to inform public health sector based on surveillance components focusing on animals and the environment. Evaluation of several surveillance systems under a large project with predefined aims facilitates a common direction for the surveillance systems, and allows for benchmarking, for specific pathogens or diseases across countries. This will form a strong foundation for addressing the Need 1 and the related Specific Objectives 1-3.

OH4Surveillance work package 3 will arrange webinars that will aid in training and dissemination of the OH-EpiCap tool to support the participating countries to conduct the evaluations of a selection of their surveillance systems. Work package 3 will also facilitate sharing of lessons learned from the evaluation, across countries and across surveillance activities. Key observations are included in regular reporting to HaDEA, as well as in the Interim Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.2) and at the Final Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.3).

Summary

The evaluation plan for OH4Surveillance is structured under three levels of indicators: action level, project level and surveillance activity level indicators. The key strategy applied is that evaluation takes place throughout the project, thus allowing addressing relevant observations during the project lifetime.

References

Tegegne, H. A., Bogaardt, C., Collineau, L., Cazeau, G., Lailier, R., Reinhardt, J., Freeth, F. T. A., Taylor, E., Prada, J. M., & Hénaux, V. (2023). OH-EpiCap: a semi-quantitative tool for the evaluation of One Health epidemiological surveillance capacities and capabilities. *Frontiers in public health*, 11, 1053986. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1053986>

